

AN IN-SITU STUDY OF THE FRACTURE MECHANISMS OF SiCw/AZ91 MAGNESIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: In this paper, the fracture processes of squeeze cast SiCw/AZ91 magnesium matrix composites were studied with in-situ scanning electron microscope (SEM) and transmission electron microscope (TEM) tensile techniques. When the composite was loaded, plastic deformation took place in local stress concentration regions, then developed into microcrack. A large number of microcracks initiated in the matrix and these cracks linked abruptly, resulting in catastrophic fracture of the composite. The results indicated that the poor ductility of the composites was attributed to the local stress concentration because of the addition of the whiskers and the low inherent ductility of the matrix magnesium alloy. The fracture processes of the composites was matrix-controlled.

KEYWORDS: Magnesium alloy, SiC whisker, metal matrix composites, squeeze cast, in-situ SEM, In-situ TEM, tensile, microcrack, fracture.

INTRODUCTION

Magnesium alloys are becoming increased favored for structural application. This is not only due to their relatively low density, which can reduce weight and save energy substantially, but also due to their good damping capacity, castability and mechinability. However, the disadvantages of relatively low strength at room and elevated temperature, low elastic modulus and wear resistance, and poor corrosion resistance, restrict their use in applications where stringent requirements must be met. Magnesium alloys reinforced with discontinuous phases, such as short fibers [1-2], particles [3-6], or whiskers [7-8] can eliminate all the disadvantages except for poor corrosion resistance, showing that magnesium matrix composites have increasing potential in automotive, high performance defense and aerospace applications.

However, the poor ductility and fracture toughness limited their use in many structural applications. The strain to failure was often around 1% in these composites. In order to widen their application areas, low ductility of the composites has to be improved.

Compared with Al-MMCs, only a few studies [5-6, 9-11] have been reported on the fracture mechanisms of discontinuously reinforced Mg-MMCs, the fracture mechanisms of the composites are poorly understood.

As for SiCw/Al composites, much effort has been focused on their fracture mechanisms, the mechanical properties of the matrix, whisker, interface between whisker and matrix, and coarse intermetallic particles play important roles in the fracture behavior of the composites.

Several techniques have been used to study the fracture behavior of metal matrix composites. SEM fractography analysis, SEM and TEM examination of the crack path in controlled fracture test specimens which were stopped and unloaded just prior to unstable crack growth [11], are based on observation of damaged microstructure of postmortem samples, providing no further information on the critical events in fracture process. In-situ SEM and TEM tensile techniques can provide dynamic observation of the crack initiation and propagation. In-situ SEM tensile technique can only be used to observe the changes of surface microstructure, while in-situ TEM straining technique can give more information, such as the emission and motion of dislocations in the process of deformation, site of crack initiation, propagation path, as well as the effect of interface and precipitates on the crack initiation and propagation.

Because of the HCP crystal structure of Mg alloys, the fracture mechanism of Mg-MMCs is different from that of Al-MMCs. To elucidate the relationship between fracture micromechanisms and microstructure of the composites, dynamic observation of fracture processes in squeeze cast SiCw/AZ91 magnesium matrix composites was performed with in-situ SEM and TEM tensile techniques.

EXPERIMENTAL

The materials used in this study were SiCw/AZ91 magnesium matrix composites fabricated by squeeze casting method. Commercial heat treatable AZ91 magnesium alloy (8.5-9.5% Al, 0.45-0.90% Zn, 0.15-0.30% Mn, 0.20% Si, 0.01% Ni, balance Mg) was used as matrix, TWS-100 β -SiC whisker was used as reinforcement whose volume fraction in preform is 20% without binder. Squeeze casting was carried out by pouring molten AZ91 overheated to 800°C into the SiC whisker preform, which was preheated to 800°C and placed in the squeeze cast mold preheated to 300°C, and then by infiltrating the melt into the preform under the pressure of 100 MPa. The processes of melting and pouring were performed under CO₂/SF₆ atmosphere.

The specimens used for in-situ SEM tensile were machined from the above squeeze casting ingot into thin plates, the dimensions of which were shown in previous work [12]. A sharp notch (0.2 mm in depth, 0.1mm in width) was made in the center of the specimens by electric discharge machining (EDM). For clear observation, the observation surfaces of the specimens were metallographically polished. In-situ SEM tensile processes were performed with a HITACHI S-570 SEM equipped with a tensile stage, the strain rate was about $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S}^{-1}$.

The in-situ TEM tensile specimens with dimension of $3 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ were also prepared from squeeze casting composites, and mechanically ground into 0.3 mm thick thin foils, then dimpled with Gatan dimpler, finally were ion milled to perforation using a liquid nitrogen cold stage to prevent heating during the ion milling process. In-situ TEM tensile processes were performed in a H-800 TEM equipped with a strain stage operating at 175 KV.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fracture behavior of discontinuously reinforced MMCs is very sensitive to the reinforcement, the interface and the matrix, although it is difficult to identify clearly the dominant mechanism and contributions by each mechanism. Dynamic observation with in-situ tensile techniques make it possible to suggest the dominant mechanism and its contributions.

From in-situ SEM dynamic observation, it is found that when load was applied, microcracks started to be initiated at the ends of whisker and damaged whiskers, as shown in Fig.1. Some microcracks in the matrix can also be observed. When applied load increased, major crack formed at the center of the precrack and some microcracks formed around the crack tip, see Fig.2. When high load was applied, major crack grew to some extent, but more microcracks formed in the matrix and some microcracks linked together. After applying more load, microcracks linked together abruptly, leading to the catastrophic failure of the composites along a direction perpendicular to the applied stress axis.

Fig.1: Microcracks initiated at (a) whisker ends, (b) damaged whiskers.

Fig.2: Major crack formed in the composites.

In order to further observe the microstructural changes in the composites in the case of deformation and fracture, in-situ TEM tensile was performed, which can give more information, such as the emission of dislocations in the process of deformation, as well as the influence of interface and precipitates on the crack initiation and propagation. Although the stress conditions between the TEM foil specimen and bulk material are different, the former is under plane stress condition, the latter is under plane strain condition, dynamic observation can provide insight into the poor ductility of the composites[13].

As the thin foil was loaded, crack initiated at the edge of the perforation perpendicular to the tensile direction, accompanied by the emission of dislocations which went ahead quickly to form dislocation free zone(DFZ) at the crack tip, as shown in Fig.3. It also can be seen that the motion direction of the dislocations was changed because of the pile up of dislocations at the interface. At the same time, the original dislocations existing in the matrix also went ahead.

Fig.3: Interaction between dislocations and SiC whiskers, (a) pile up of dislocations at interface, (b) motion of dislocations after further straining.

After further loading, a large number of microcracks formed in the magnesium matrix, and local thinning appeared to occur during the microcrack formation. Most of local thinning and microcracks were adjacent to the SiC whiskers, as shown in Fig.4. Dislocations stacked in local thinning regions.

With increase in the applied load, some microcracks propagated, and some local thinning developed to microcracks. Upon further straining, these microcracks quickly linked together, leading to catastrophic fracture of the composites, along a direction perpendicular to the tensile axis of the specimen.

Fig.4: Local thinning and microcracks formed in the composites.

Fig.5: Interaction between propagating crack and SiC whisker, (a) crack blunted at a whisker, (b) crack bypassed the whisker after further straining.

Because the regions in the vicinity of the whisker are stress concentration sites, local thinning and microcracks initiated in these regions, the interface between the matrix and whisker accelerated the crack growth. On the other hand, the interface prohibited the crack propagation, the dislocations piling up at the interface forced the crack to change its propagation direction and bypass whisker, as shown in Fig.5. The former effect was more evident.

Fig.6 shows the crack propagation path in the composite, there is less evidence of whisker cracking and interface debonding, the bond of the interface between the matrix and the whisker was relatively strong. And cracks propagated mainly through the matrix, indicating a matrix-controlled fracture mechanism.

Fig.6: The path of crack propagation in the composites.

The in-situ TEM fracture process was almost as same as the results obtained by in-situ SEM tensile technique. The whole composite fracture process is as follows: local thinning and microcracks initiated, microcracks linked with each other leading to catastrophic fracture of the composites, there was no single major crack forming in the in-situ TEM fracture process.

Due to the large difference in CTE between Mg and SiC whisker, severe stress concentration arised in the Mg matrix adjacent to the Mg-SiCw interface. Because of the limited number of active slip systems available for plastic deformation in the magnesium alloys (h.c.p.Crystal structure), their ability of deformation is poor. During the process of deformation, because the local stress concentration can not be easily relaxed by plastic deformation of the matrix, many microcracks formed in the matrix nearby the matrix - whisker interface at the very low stress. Fast weakest linkage of these microcracks resulted in the catastrophic failure of the composites. The fracture process was matrix-controlled.

CONCLUSIONS

1. A large number of local thinning and microcracks formed at very low stress, fast weakest linkage of these microcracks resulted in the catastrophic failure of the SiCw/AZ91 magnesium matrix composites. No single major crack formed in the in-situ TEM fracture process.

2. Inhomogeneous distribution of stress and exhaustion of local plasticity was responsible for the poor ductility of the SiCw/AZ91 composites. The fracture mechanism was matrix-controlled.

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